

Cover

Article: La compra pública d'innovació com instrument facilitador per a l'adopció de les innovacions basades en valor al sector salut

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p><i>(Translation from the original abstract in Catalan)</i></p>	<p>Healthcare innovation arises from unmet clinical, organizational, and societal needs, driving the development of new technologies, services, and care models. According to the WHO “3D” framework—discovery, development, and delivery—many innovations fail during deployment due to limited evidence of cost-effectiveness and sustainability in real-world settings. Barriers such as heterogeneous reimbursement schemes, lack of interoperability standards, and weak interaction between healthcare demand and industrial supply hinder large-scale adoption. The Whole System Demonstrator programme in England highlighted this challenge, showing improved patient outcomes but insufficient economic efficiency because of implementation costs. In this context, Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) represents a strategic mechanism to accelerate the adoption of value-based innovations by aligning healthcare needs, procurement policies, and market-driven innovation, thereby facilitating sustainable integration into clinical practice.</p>